

**Assessing Fruit Peel Fiber's Utilization and Efficiency
in Sustainable Paper Production: A Comprehensive Analysis of Lignin
Content and pH Levels to its Physical Properties**

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the potential correlation of a fruit peel's lignin content and pH level to the paper produced from it, in hopes to optimize the paper industry's efficiency and sustainability by identifying the most suitable raw material (in this case, waste fruit peel) for each kind of paper production.

For this experiment, banana (*Musa paradisiaca*), apple (*Malus domestica*), orange (*Citrus sinensis*), papaya (*Carica papaya*), grape (*Vitis vinifera*), and kiwi (*Actinidia deliciosa*) peels were utilized to give a proper variety of pH levels and lignin contents towards the formation of paper. There are 2 stages in making the fruit peel paper, first is the making of the pulp and second is the making of the paper itself.

To make the pulp, equal masses of fruit peels were boiled separately, first in a solution of water and baking soda, and afterwards only in water for 15 minutes each. Then, they were blended with waste paper that had been soaked in hot water with a ratio of 1:1, along with 50 ml of hot water and sieved.

For the making of the paper, 5g of each fruit pulp was flattened on a surface of equal areas, dabbed with a towel and then left outside to dry under the sun for 2 days. Each paper's physical properties were then tested and compared with their respective lignin content and pH levels. The results showed that the lignin content of a fruit is proportional to the paper's stiffness and water absorbance ability, while its pH level did not have an effect.

I . Introduction

1.1 Background

Over the last few years, a plethora of environmental issues has proved itself as a worthy adversary to a comfortable life. Be it due to climate change and the unpredictable weather it causes or the decrease in air quality due to pollution, it has affected human lives too much to ignore. The overgrowing population has caused an ecological overshoot, however industries are still faced with the challenge of meeting every individual's needs and wants. As a compromise to this issue, many industries have begun to shift towards a sustainable approach, particularly evident in companies adopting eco-friendly packaging for their products. In fact, according to a survey conducted, as of 2022, 67% of companies have started implementing sustainable materials and 66% are working to increase their energy efficiency. This trend has popularized fruit peels in the paper industry. Rich in cellulose and lignin, the primary components of paper, they appear to be worthy sustainable alternatives. Though there are numerous fruit peel based paper that already exists in the market, this experiment hopes to increase the efficiency of its manufacturing process by identifying the raw materials best suited for each use, so that there may be less additives and environmentally hazardous steps involved.

The pH of raw materials plays a crucial role in the chemistry of papermaking. Aligning with the Arrhenius theory, cellulose is highly affected by the pH of its environment. There are two main chemical pathways to paper degradation: the depolymerization of cellulose through hydrolysis, which weakens paper, and the oxidation of the glucopyranose unit. The oxidation

specifically occurs on the hydroxyl groups on the C(2), C(3), and C(6) atoms, causing discoloration through the formation of carboxylic groups. Glycosidic bonds in cellulose are only known to be stable in alkaline and neutral environments but degrade in acidic conditions due to an increased concentration of hydronium ions (H_3O^+), leading to shortened cellulose chains and reduced polymerization. These changes in the cellulose structures may impact the hydrophilic nature of the paper. Since hydrophilicity relies on intermolecular forces, changes in cellulose structure may affect the paper's ability to form hydrogen bonds with water molecules, affecting its water absorption. In this experiment, the Arrhenius theory will serve as a baseline in unraveling the dynamics during this papermaking process.

Lignin ($C_{81}H_{92}O_{28}$) is a natural complex polymer found in plant cell walls. The synthesis of lignin involves the radical polymerization of three constituent monomers: p-coumaryl alcohol, coniferyl alcohol, and sinapyl alcohol. This process results in the formation of p-hydroxyphenyl (H), guaiacyl (G), and syringyl (S) lignin subunits. As lignin exhibits structural diversity due to the random nature of this polymerization, it is easily susceptible to oxidation, making papers with high lignin content sensitive to degradation processes. It serves a dual role in cellulose degradation as an oxidation catalyst and an antioxidant. Research by William James Barrow shows that paper acidity is crucial in decreasing tensile properties during natural aging. Though, it is still uncertain whether the acidic pH is due to lignin or other factors. Due to this, the Kraft process has been a staple in the paper industry, enabling manufacturers to efficiently reduce lignin and control the paper's structural integrity.

However, the Kraft process brings about numerous environmental concerns as it involves many harmful chemicals and changes in the molecular structure of lignin. Specifically, in this process, lignin will be repolymerized with increased C-C bonds between aromatic constituents at the cost of weaker oxygen-containing bonds. This will make the lignin extracted more resistant to depolymerization and thus, less sustainable.

This research aims to identify an alternative method. Specifically, by utilizing fruit peels, a common waste product containing fibers, cellulose, and necessary chemical compounds, for paper making. Nowadays, there are already numerous fruit-based papers in use. However, in hopes to further improve efficiency in the industry, this experiment will involve comparing each fruit peel's properties to the resultant papers, so that unnecessary processes and additives may be avoided as much as possible.

Additionally, fruit peels naturally have a lower lignin content compared to wood pulp, so it may reduce the need for the Kraft process, making the papermaking process more sustainable. As mentioned above, there are many speculations that the lignin content of a paper and its acidity are tied together. Hence, when creating paper from fruit peels, it only seems logical to take these factors, inherent in the peels, into account for a proper comparison in their paper quality and property in order to identify their most efficient uses.

1.2 Research Objectives

This research aims to:

- Evaluate the effects of lignin content and pH level to the paper quality and properties (in terms of water resistance, absorption ability, thickness, foldability (stiffness))
- Analyze each fruit peel paper's properties so that the paper industry may identify raw materials (in this case, fruit peels) best suited for the production of each type of paper

II . Methodology

2.1 Materials

Various fruit peel wastes—orange, banana, apple, papaya, grapes, and kiwis—a digital balance, blender, waste papers, boiling pan, baking soda, 200 ml measuring cylinder, pH indicator, sieve, scissors, spoon, stopwatch, micrometer, measuring spoon, identical flat square lids, and a hair dryer (optional)

2.2 Experimental Design

The process of making pulps out of the fruit peels

To truly explore how lignin content can influence the characteristics of the resultant fruit peel paper, fruit peels with various different lignin contents were used, namely apples, bananas, grapes, oranges, papayas, and kiwis. The fruit peels were first weighed on a digital balance in an identical container to show 30.00 g as a constant variable in this experiment. The container alone

weighed 18.30 g, so the utilized fruit peels weighed exactly 11.70 g, respectively. Each fruit peel was then cut into approximately 1.5 cm bits and separately boiled, first in 200 ml of pure water and afterwards in 200 ml with 2 g of baking soda for 15 minutes each. This acts as a pretreatment method to extract fibers and facilitate the breakdown of their cellular structures, as due to baking soda's (sodium bicarbonate) alkalinity, the fruit peels are able to go through alkaline hydrolysis of their ester linkages and hemicellulose to liberate fibers and increase their extractability.

Then the cooked peels were run through water to remove any possible remnants of the baking soda. The waste papers used in this experiment were old newspapers. Using the digital balance, they were weighed to be 18.30 g too, to be in a 1:1 ratio with the fruit peels, then cut into smaller pieces and soaked in hot water to soften them. Afterwards, the resultant waste papers were blended with the fruit peels along with 50 ml of hot water. The resultant mixture is then sieved to separate the pulp from the liquid.

The process of making paper out of fruit pulp

Using the digital balance, 5 g of each fruit pulp is put onto the rectangular surface as a mold and flattened so that it fits. Using a towel, it is then lightly dabbed to absorb some more excess water and let out to dry under the sun for 2 days. In this experiment, the orange fruit peel still wasn't able to dry completely after 2 days, so a hair dryer was used to speed up the process. Afterwards, cut off the sides of the paper to the shape of the mold exactly.

Measurement of Lignin and pH Level

Due to the lack of equipment, such as the spectrophotometer, the Klason method could not be performed experimentally to find out the exact lignin content of the fruit peels used. Thus, to overcome this limitation, the values of each fruit peel's lignin content were derived and averaged based on the values given on the internet. Meanwhile, pH levels were measured using pH indicator strips by placing them into the fruit peel extract that remained after boiling it the first time with just pure water and comparing them to the scale given in its container.

Measuring the Physical Properties of the Resultant Papers

This experiment aimed to compare the physical characteristics of the fruit peel papers, namely their ability to absorb and resist water, fold, thickness, and smell. To be able to do all these tests, each paper was divided into four equal parts to perform different tests. One for the liquid absorbance test, one for the water resistance test, one for the folding, measuring of thickness, and smell test, and one extra just in case of the need for repetition.

To measure its ability to absorb water, the fruit peel paper was first placed on a digital balance to measure its mass. Then, it was immersed in a container filled with water and left to sit there for about 5 minutes. Afterwards, it was taken out, and its mass was measured again. The difference in mass was then found by subtracting its final mass from its initial mass. This value was then used as a means to compare it with other fruit peel papers so that the correlation between its lignin content and water absorption ability could be observed.

Secondly, to find out how resistant the paper was to liquid, a different piece of fruit peel paper was immersed in water once again. Using a stopwatch, the paper was lifted from the water every 10 seconds and shaken to see if it would break apart, and repeated until it did so or until the time exceeded 300 seconds. This is by no means a precise way to measure the water resistance and absorption ability; however, the use of this method is just to compare each paper's value in relation to each other's lignin content values.

The third piece of paper would be used to measure the paper's thickness, ability to fold, and smell. To measure the thickness of the paper, a micrometer was used. First, it was made sure to be properly calibrated. Then, the paper was placed between the jaws of the micrometer so that a reading could be taken from it. Because of the small readings and, hence, the higher percentage of error, this measurement was repeated three times and then averaged for a more accurate value. Afterwards, the paper was folded along opposite sides to assess its durability, and it smelled. The collected data was then collected and noted down on a table (Table 2).

III. Results and Discussion

Figure 1. Fruit Peel Paper Formed Before Cutting

Figure 2. Fruit Peel Paper After being Cut

Figure 3. Lignin Content and pH Levels in Fruit Peels

Type of Fruit peel	Lignin Content (%)	pH Level
apple	19.40	3.4
banana	14.47	5.1
grape	21.50	3.8
kiwi	29.93	3.7
orange	8.90	3.2
papaya	14.30	5.0

Figure 4. Experimental Results: Physical Properties of the Fruit Peel Papers

Type of fruit peel paper	Approximate time in water before it broke apart / s	Mass difference of paper after being submerged in water / g	Thickness / mm	Fold test	Smell
apple	50	1.43	0.41	Yes, but slightly	None

				cracked	
banana	>300	1.39	0.45	Yes, but very slightly cracked	None
grape	100	1.45	0.41	Yes, but barely intact after	Very slight
kiwi	80	1.61	0.42	Yes, but barely intact after	Very slight
orange	>300	1.30	0.49	Yes	Yes, quite prominent
papaya	60	1.35	0.45	Yes, but slightly cracked	Very slight

4.1 Comparison of the Physical Properties of the Fruit Peel Paper to their respective Lignin Content

Based on the results of the study, the effects of the lignin content of the fruit peel used may affect the physical properties of the paper produced. The tables above (see Figures 3 and 4) can be used to compare the relation of lignin content to each physical property in the line graph as follows:

Figure 5.

Lignin Content (%) and Mass difference of paper after being submerged in water / g

The amount of water absorbed is generally directly proportional to the lignin content (see Figure 5). In other words, as the lignin content in the fruit increases, the more the paper is able to absorb water. For this particular experiment, it can be seen based on the table that the best liquid absorbent amongst the fruit peel papers is the kiwi. On a molecular level, this could be explained by the hydrophilic nature of lignin.

Though lignin is known to have both polar and nonpolar regions due to its hyperbranched structure, there is a higher tendency for lignin to be polar. These polar groups (i.e., hydroxyl (-OH) groups) can interact with water through hydrogen bonding, making these particular regions water-attracting or hydrophilic, thus helping the paper produced to also absorb more water. However, for those with lower lignin levels, such as oranges, it could be said that the overall hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance of the paper skews more towards the hydrophobic side as they exhibit fewer interactions with water molecules.

Figure 6.

Based on Figure 6, the amount of time taken for the paper to break apart after being exposed to water is not in any way related to its lignin content. In other words, the lignin content does not affect one's water-resistant ability. Though, by theory, lignin's hydrophobic properties should have an effect on its water resistance, we can conclude that it has very little to no effect and is hugely overshadowed by other factors of the fruit peels, such as their natural wax and cellulose content.

Figure 7.

The experiment conducted showed that in general, as the lignin content increases, the thickness of the paper produced decreases, with an exception for the kiwi peel paper (see Figure 7). As lignin is used to stiffen paper, it is commonly associated with thicker paper; however, this experiment proves otherwise. Though it is worth considering that lignin in fruit peels may differ from wood pulp lignin due to their respective compositions, such as the presence of cellulose and antioxidants in fruit peels, this may have affected this result. Additionally, boiling the fruit peels with baking soda may have altered some chemical compositions due to its alkalinity, affecting how lignin interacts with other components.

As for its ability to fold, we can see that the fruit peels that contain lower lignin content are more able to be folded than those with higher lignin contents (see Figure 4). Hence, we can conclude that higher lignin contents produce stiffer paper. This aligns with the conventional use of lignin in papermaking, as mentioned above. Overall, the lignin levels of fruit peels do seem to

have a correlation to the physical properties of the resultant paper in terms of its water absorption and stiffness.

4.2 Comparison of the Physical Properties of the Fruit Peel Paper to their respective pH Levels

Based on the results of the study, the effects of the pH level of the fruit peel used are insignificant to the physical properties of the paper produced. The data from the tables above (Figures 3 and 4) can be used to compare the relation of pH level to each physical property in the line graph as follows:

Figure 8.

Figure 9.

Figure 10.

Figures 8, 9 and 10 show randomly scattered points without any visible trends; hence, it is safe to say that the pH level of the fruit peel used has no correlation with water absorption or resistance ability, as well as the thickness of the produced fruit peel paper. Though some may argue that despite the points in Figure 9 seeming equally random, there is a significant difference in the time taken for paper to fall apart after being immersed in water for the most acidic and alkali fruit peel, which may suggest an optimal pH range for water resistance. However, this can be disregarded as it does not align with scientific conventions. Given that cellulose is a complex carbohydrate made up of units linked by β -1,4-glycosidic bonds that give its molecular structure strength and rigidity, too much of an acidic or alkali condition will give rise to pH-dependent hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds in cellulose, weakening its structure and hence water resistance. Now suppose those two pH levels were the optimal pH range. It is still doubtful to believe that, as the data on the pH range in between them is still scattered. Hence, it's more plausible that the pH level has no significant effect on the paper's water resistance. The same logic applies to Figure 10 as well.

When it comes to the ability of the paper to fold, there seems to be no correlation with its constituent fruit peel's pH level. Both fruit peels with similar pH, such as grape and kiwi, with a pH of 3.8 and 3.7, respectively, and completely different pH, such as apple and papaya, with a pH of 3.4 and 5.0, respectively, seemed to be similar in their ability to fold; thus, no pattern can be drawn from this. Overall, it can be said that pH levels do not affect the resultant paper in any significant way.

4.3 Implications for Sustainable Paper Production

Through this experiment, the correlation between lignin levels and the resultant paper's physical properties can be better understood, which may allow for a more efficient use and selection of materials in papermaking processes. Fruits with higher lignin contents, such as kiwis, can be used for packaging or printing due to their stiffness, as well as filter paper or cleaning materials due to their ability to absorb liquid better. By being able to identify raw materials that already have similar levels of certain components to the desired product, less energy would be used up in the process of manufacturing it as there wouldn't be much to change chemically.

The reduced reliance on machines or chemical additives will then help avoid increasing environmental concerns, helping increase sustainability. For example, in this scenario, specifically the paper-making process, the Kraft Process can be reduced, helping preserve lignin as opposed to burning it for energy or discarding it as a byproduct, which may both cause air pollution.

IV. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the scientific viability of utilizing fruit peel fibers in papermaking, considering lignin content and pH levels. Based on this experiment, although pH levels do not show any apparent effects on the fruit peel paper made, the lignin content can be tied to the physical properties such as the liquid absorbance ability and stiffness of the resultant

paper. The positive outcomes for this in fruit peels suggest a promising avenue for sustainable paper production, encouraging further research and development in this domain to further improve efficiency in the use of raw materials.

V. Recommendations for Future Research

Future research endeavors should focus on refining the papermaking process. This could be done by exploring additional properties that they may have as well as extra steps that could be implemented to further increase their durability. It is also encouraged for those who have equipment available to them to conduct direct experimentation to find the values of the lignin content of the specific fruit peels used for a more accurate result. As mentioned above, the oxidation of cellulose may speed up the degradation of paper, so it is worth conducting research into the levels of antioxidants in the fruit peels and their potential effects on improving the durability of papers.

VI. References

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